

Development of Bio-based, Hazardous Air Pollutant Free Sheet Molding Compounds

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ABSTRACT

Chemically modified soybean oil could be an inexpensive alternative to petroleum- derived unsaturated polyester SMC (sheet molding compound) resins. When reinforced with natural fibers, these composites could yield properties similar to commercial SMCs. This study investigates the synthesis conditions of natural fiber reinforced soybean oil SMCs.

Keywords: *biocomposites, sheet molding compounds, soybean oil, natural fibers*

INTRODUCTION

Sheet molding compounds (SMCs) are widely used in military, automotive, aircraft, and structural applications [1-7]. These materials can be made of phenolic, unsaturated polyester, or vinyl ester resins, in addition to containing fiber reinforcers, thickeners, and low profile additives to enhance the performance. Major features of the SMC resin come from its capability of exhibiting thickening behavior, and being able to further carry out polymerization during molding [2, 8]. However, since some of the commonly used resins for SMC processing are petroleum-derived and are known to release styrene emissions or other hazardous air pollutants (HAPs), there is a strong need for developing inexpensive and more eco- friendly SMCs.

Synthetic reinforcers like carbon, aramid, and glass fibers offer many benefits such as controlled processing and high tensile properties [9]. Unfortunately, these fibers have many disadvantages including health hazards for workers, abrasiveness, higher density and cost [8, 10]. Because of this, natural fibers are considered as attractive alternatives for synthetic fibers since they have low cost, are lightweight, and come from renewable resources [11, 12]. However, chemical treatment should be done to further enhance the mechanical properties of the fibers [11, 12].

The objective of the study is to modify the bio-based resin and natural fiber components to produce composites with comparable mechanical and thermal properties as commercial SMCs. Fiber treatment and chemical modification to the soybean oil is studied. Each of these components is expected to have strong effects on the final properties of the cured biocomposites. This work investigates the effects of each component, in respect to its chemical composition, in order to produce the most favorable SMC biocomposite formulation.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Soybean oil pre-polymer synthesis

The methods for the synthesis of the prepolymer can be found in [10]. Acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESO) (Cytec Surface Specialties) and 0.1wt% hydroquinone (Fisher Scientific) were mixed together using a mechanical stirrer. Hydroquinone was used to prevent self-polymerization. A water bath was used to heat the mixture to 75 °C. At ~75 °C, finely grounded maleic anhydride (MA) (Sigma-Aldrich) was added to the flask and mixed until homogeneous. MA was added to correspond to a 0.5:1, 1:1, and 2:1 mol ratios of MA: AESO. The temperature was increased to ~85 °C as 1.85wt% of *N, N*-dimethylbenzylamine (DMBA) (Sigma-Aldrich) catalyst was added to the mixture. Constant stirring and heating at 85±3 °C was maintained for 2 hours. The modified soybean oil pre-polymer will be referred to as MAESO (maleated acrylated epoxidized soybean oil). Structures of the AESO and MAESO monomers are shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively.

Figure 1. AESO structure

Figure 2. MAESO pre-polymer

Bio-based resin synthesis

The resin formulation consisted of 67 wt% pre-polymer and 33 wt% styrene co-monomer. The free radical initiator, t-butyl peroxy benzoate (TBP), Sigma-Aldrich, was added in the amount of 1.4 wt% of the total resin weight. After mixing the appropriate amounts of pre-polymer and co-monomer, the samples were placed in a vacuum oven for 20-30 minutes to allow the volatiles to escape. This step was extremely critical, in order to prevent severe cracking in the cured resins. After vacuuming, the samples were cured for 2 hours at 115 °C and post-cured for 2 hours at 150 °C.

A commercial, unsaturated polyester SMC was used to serve as a target resin. This was done to determine properties and behavior of currently used SMC polyester resins under similar experimental conditions. The commercial resin used was Atryl TCA resin provided by AOC Resins. This resin will be referred to as PE for polyester.

Alkali Fiber Treatment

Bast kenaf fibers were soaked in a 7 wt% solution of NaOH at room temperature. The fibers were cut to an average length of 44 mm prior to treatment. Next, kenaf fibers were soaked for 30 minutes, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 24 hours. After treatment, the fibers were rinsed with distilled water until a neutral pH was obtained. The fibers were then vacuum dried in an oven for 24 hours at 80 °C to help remove residual moisture. Finally, the fibers were transferred to a conditioning chamber where they were kept according to ASTM conditions at 65% R.H. and ~21 °C for 72 hrs.

Thermo-mechanical Analysis

TMA studies on the cured polyester and soybean oil resins were conducted using a TA Instruments 2940 Thermo-mechanical Analyzer. TMA was used in order to study the changes in dimensional stability and to determine the T_g . The samples were subjected to a constant pre-load force of 0.025N. All samples were measured to be approximately 1.65-1.75 μ m in thickness. The cured resins were equilibrated at 30 °C, and then ramped from 30 °C to 300 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min.

Rheometry

TA Instruments AR2000 Rheometer was used to determine the rheological behavior of the MAESO monomer. Steady state shear experiments were carried out at room temperature on the AESO and MAESO monomers. Additionally, the viscosities of the pre-cured resins were tested. All experiments were performed using a peltier plate geometry. The shear rate of the samples was varied between 0.01-100 1/s and 1-100 1/s, depending on the fluid. The samples were also sheared in the reverse rate direction to determine if there was any indication of shear history.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy was carried out using a Jeol JSM 5800 with an accelerating voltage of 15kV to determine the changes resulting from the alkali treatment on the surface of the kenaf fibers. The samples were sputtered with a Hummer 6.2 by ANATECH LTD to help eliminate charging on the samples while imaging.

Attenuated total reflectance infrared (ATR-IR) spectroscopy

ATR-IR spectroscopy was carried out on alkali treated kenaf fibers to determine the physical changes that occurred on the fiber surface following treatment. The ATR-IR characterization of fibers was done as a function of treatment time. An ATR diamond crystal plate was used and 64 scans were collected for each spectrum. A resolution of 4 cm^{-1} was used.

Fiber Bundle Tensile Testing

To test the mechanical properties of treated and untreated kenaf fiber bundles, fibers were subjected to tensile testing. After conditioning for 72 hours, the mechanical behavior

of kenaf fiber bundles was characterized using an Instron 5566. Kenaf fiber bundles were mounted on paper tabs, secured with scotch tape and superglue, and tested using an effective gauge length of 30 mm. A 100 N load cell was used with a strain rate of 0.04/min. The software used to analyze the data was Bluehill version 1.2. At least 15 specimens were tested for each treatment time. There were approximately 3-5 fibers/bundle. The average diameters of the fibers were determined using an optical microscope with 10x magnification. Due to the fibers ranging in size, the average fiber bundle diameter was determined by measuring the diameter at the top, middle, and bottom portions for each of the bundles, then taking the average of those measurements for each specimen.

Figure 3. Volume changes in cured resins as a function of temperature

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dimensional Stability of chemical modified soybean oil resins

All cured resins were studied using thermomechanical analysis. Dimensional stability behavior of the MAESO-styrene resins was compared to that of the commercial PE resins. In figure 3, it was observed that the sample showing the greatest dimensional changes with a temperature increase was the cured AESO-styrene sample. This is more than likely due to not much crosslinking taking place in the sample. The major purposes for adding maleic anhydride to AESO is to increase polarity and reactivity of the sample. This would make it possible for more crosslinking to take place, thereby, increasing the rigidity. The 0.5:1 MAESO/styrene sample was the next sample that showed the most dimensional changes as the temperature increased. The 1:1 MAESO/styrene, 2:1 MAESO/styrene and PE samples showed the lowest dimensional changes at higher temperatures. Between 25-100 °C, the commercial PE sample appeared to be the most dimensionally stable, which would be expected of the PE due to its higher glass transition (T_g) temperature. The T_g in TMA experiments can be found by extrapolation, and recording the temperature where the onset of the largest slope change occurs in the curves.

Therefore, the T_g of the commercial PE appears at $\sim 127^\circ\text{C}$, while the T_g ranges for all other soybean-based samples appear between $50\text{-}75^\circ\text{C}$. On the other hand, the T_g of the 2:1 MAESO/styrene resin was fairly low compared to the PE target resin.

The 2:1 MAESO/styrene sample did appear to be the most dimensionally stable compared to all of the other soybean-based resins. This could possibly be attributed to the higher level of maleinization in the sample. This suggests that more crosslinking took place, because there were more maleate groups present to react with the styrene co-monomer. These values for the MAESO/ styrene resins are much lower than those appearing in [10]. This could be the result of several factors. One reason could be that although the level of maleinization for the 2:1 MAESO pre-polymers was highest, the degree of crosslinking was still quite low. Another factor could be that some of the styrene co-monomer had evaporated during curing, especially when curing at temperatures exceeding 100°C . The final reason could relate to moisture intake in the samples from humidity. To alleviate this, future samples will be studied under more controlled environmental conditions to eliminate any external influences of environmental conditions on sample behavior.

Figure 4. Rheological behavior of MAESO and effect of maleinization on viscosity

According to figure 4, all soybean oil monomers showed Newtonian behavior where the viscosity was constant independent of shear rate. It was observed that the viscosity increased as the level of maleinization increased. The viscosity increase can be attributed to an increase in intermolecular interaction caused by the addition of more polar groups from maleic anhydride [13].

Figure 5 shows that styrene was added to the MAESO monomer to determine how the addition of the co-monomer affected the rheological behavior. From the figure, it appeared that the 2:1 MAESO/ styrene sample still showed Newtonian behavior after the addition of the styrene. There was also a significant decrease in the viscosity of the MAESO/styrene sample. This viscosity decrease is desired due to the resin having the ability to properly wet the fibers during processing. This would help better distribute the fibers throughout the composite. On the other hand, the commercial PE with its added co-

monomer appeared to show non-Newtonian behavior. The viscosity was observed to increase with time as the sample was sheared. Since the PE sample was not sheared at a constant rate, this sample is not considered as a rheopectic fluid.

Figure 5. Effect of styrene co-monomer addition on viscosity of 2:1 MAESO monomers

Physical changes of alkali treatment on kenaf fiber surface

Figure 6 shows SEM images of kenaf fibers as a function of alkali treatment time. It was observed that the fibers appeared cleaner and rougher as the treatment time increased. The roughness was believed to be attributed to an increase in fibrillation of fiber, which would lead to better dispersion of individual fibers in a matrix and also improve the fiber-matrix interface leading to enhanced mechanical properties. Other studies for natural fibers showed evidence supporting the claim that alkali treatment of kenaf fibers aided in removing fiber surface impurities and increasing the mechanical properties [11, 12].

Figure 7 shows the ATR-IR spectra for the physical changes that occurred in kenaf alkali treated fibers. From the spectra, it was observed that the peak for the as-received fibers located at $\sim 1730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappeared in as short as 30 minutes following treatment. This peak could be attributed to activity taking place in the carbonyl region, primarily from the removal of carboxyl or ester linkages from sugars in hemicellulose [14] or pectin. The peak located at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ believed to be the C=C peak from lignin appeared to decrease as alkali treatment time increased. Water also has peaks located at ~ 3300 , 1600, and 850 cm^{-1} ; however, it was believed that the majority of transformations taking place in these regions could be due to changes in surface chemistry from the removal of hemicellulose and/ or lignin.

The strong peak located at $\sim 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was observed to decrease in intensity as treatment time increased. This change could be an indication of a decrease in absorption from C-OH or C-C stretching groups, which would primarily be found in hemicellulose [15]. The absorption band at $\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in figure 7 was believed to belong to the -OH

stretching vibration in hemicellulose or cellulose. From the spectra, the peak for the hydroxyl groups was highest for fibers treated at 30 minutes. This would be expected due

Figure 7. Full ATR-IR spectra of alkali treated bast kenaf fibers.

to the fact that lignin removal occurred. Since there is now increased exposure of hemicellulose layers, more hydroxyl groups are expected to be present on the fiber surface. However, the intensity of the $-OH$ groups gradually decreased as treatment time increased. As the treatment time increased, the rate of degradation for hemicellulose is expected to increase as well. The $-OH$ band was lowest at 24 hours, which was believed to have contributed to the presence of hydroxyl groups found mostly in cellulose.

Effect of alkali treatment on fiber crystallinity

X-ray diffraction was performed on kenaf fibers before and after treatment. This technique was used in order to determine how the chemical treatment affected fiber crystallinity. It has previously been observed that alkali treatment leads to an increase in van der Waals and hydrogen-bonding as a result of the increased interaction of hydroxyl groups found in cellulose [16]. The major peak of interest in the diffractograms is the peak for cellulose, located at 2θ value of $\sim 22^\circ$ in figure 8.

The full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the crystalline peak in cellulose was also studied to obtain information about the degree of crystallinity for the treated fibers. Typically, smaller FWHM values are seen in more crystalline materials. According to table 1, the FWHM generally decreased as the treatment time increased. This was more than

Table 1. FWHM values of XRD cellulose peaks for alkali treated kenaf fibers

Sample	2θ	Average FWHM
As- received	$\sim 22.0^\circ$	1.218
30 minutes	$\sim 22.2^\circ$	1.164
2 hours	$\sim 22.2^\circ$	1.114
8 hours	$\sim 22.0^\circ$	1.012
24 hours	$\sim 22.2^\circ$	1.015

likely from the removal of amorphous pectin, hemicellulose, and lignin, and increasing exposure of semi-crystalline cellulose on the fiber surface. For this reason, it was believed that alkali treatment was somewhat effective in increasing the crystallinity.

Figure 8. X-ray diffractograms comparing the crystalline peaks kenaf fibers

Mechanical properties of kenaf fibers

X-ray diffraction data shown in figure 8 and table 1 revealed that changes took place in the crystallinity of the fibers as alkali treatment time increased. It has been observed that natural fiber mechanical property dependency lies very heavily on the level of cellulose crystallinity and orientation of crystallites [17]. Therefore, the tensile properties of kenaf fiber bundles were tested to determine if there were any significant increases in the mechanical properties.

Figures 9 (a) and (b). (a) Tensile stress and (b) E-modulus for kenaf fibers

Figures 9 (a) and (b) show the mean tensile stress and Young's modulus measurements, respectively for kenaf fibers as function of treatment times. The tensile stress increased as the treatment time increased up to an optimum point at 16 hrs. When treated for 24 hrs, the tensile stress of the fiber bundles decreased. From the data, it was observed that there was a significant difference in the tensile stress in fiber bundles when

treated for 16 and 24 hrs. This was confirmed using the F-test method, which is a statistical test used to determine if items of interest show any significant changes in standard deviation. It was observed that there were no significant changes in tensile properties of fibers treated for 30 minutes to 8 hours.

When using the F-test method to study the E-modulus, the treatment was not significant. However, the E-modulus was found to be the highest at 24 hours of treatment, which contradicts the tensile stress trends. One possible explanation for the contradictory results could be that because fiber bundles were tested, not all the fibers in the bundle failed at the same rate. As a result, zig-zag trends were observed in the stress-strain plots. Because of this, the E-modulus values may be slightly off. In this particular study, the modulus of the fiber bundles were determined by using the initial slope of the stress-strain curves. Another method may have to be employed to get more accurate results for the modulus, especially since there are not any known ASTM standards for computing the modulus for bundles of natural fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

Chemically modified soybean oil monomers and alkali treated natural fibers were studied to determine the effect of treatment or chemical modification on properties of these prospective composite reinforcers and resins, respectively. Although the MAESO containing monomers showed desirable rheological behavior and adequate dimensional stability at certain temperature ranges, the T_g was significantly lower compared to not only the PE target resins, but previous literature findings with this particular material, as well. More experiments are currently being carried out to enhance the thermal behavior of these systems. Alkali treated kenaf fibers showed many obvious changes as the treatment time was increased as opposed to fibers that were not treated. However, fiber bundle testing showed that the tensile stress values of alkali treated kenaf were statistically significant at 16-24 hours of treatment. To further enhance the treatment effects, kenaf fibers could be treated at higher temperatures to increase the removal of amorphous components in the fibers.

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